

An Improved Test for Homogeneity of Random Objects on Manifolds with Applications to Projective Shape Analysis

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Abstract

We consider an improved method of testing for the equality of two distributions on a manifold. Our method makes use of the tangential component data on the manifold in place of the embedded sample data that was previously considered in Guo, et al. (2023). We consider the tangential component-based extrinsic energy distance associated with two probability measures on a manifold embedded in a numerical space. We compare this methodology with that based on embedded sample data via simulation studies and consider a real-life application of our methodology.

Key Words: Extrinsic shape analysis, Homogeneity tests, Nash embedding, Nonparametric tests, Tangential components

1. Introduction

A test for homogeneity is a test of the equality of population distributions. Classically, homogeneity tests have been for distributions over a Euclidean space. Guo et al. (2023) developed homogeneity tests for distributions on an object space. They do this by defining the extrinsic energy distance between two probability measures on a complete metric space embedded in a Euclidean space.

Definition: (Guo et al.,2023) The extrinsic energy distance between two independent probability distributions Q_1 and Q_2 on the d -dimensional object space M relative to an embedding $j : M \rightarrow R^N$, is defined as follows

$$\varepsilon_j(Q_1, Q_2) = 2E \|j(X) - j(Y)\| - E \|j(X) - j(X')\| - E \|j(Y) - j(Y')\|$$

assuming $E \|j(X)\| < \infty$, $E \|j(Y)\| < \infty$, X, X', Y, Y' are independent r.o.'s with $P_X = P_{X'} = Q_1$ and $P_Y = P_{Y'} = Q_2$.

Guo et al. (2023) then used this distance to derive the extrinsic energy statistic test for homogeneity for the two probability distributions on the d -dimensional object space \mathcal{M} . In particular, they define the Extrinsic Energy Statistic (EE-test) as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{l, n_1, n_2} = & \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{m=1}^{n_1} \|j(X_i) - j(Y_m)\| - \frac{n_2}{nn_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{h=1}^{n_1} \|j(X_i) - j(X_h)\| \\ & - \frac{n_1}{nn_2} \sum_{l=1}^{n_2} \sum_{m=1}^{n_2} \|j(Y_l) - j(Y_m)\| \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $X_1, \dots, X_{n_1}, Y_1, \dots, Y_{n_2}$ are iid random objects. The p-value for this test is computed via the nonparametric bootstrap, which is an approximate permutation test. This is an extension of the Two-Sample E-statistic proposed by Szekely and Rizzo (2004) for Euclidean data.

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Paige and Patrangenaru (2023) used E-statistics DISTance COmponents (DISCO) methods to test for differences in mean projective shapes. In the present manuscript, we develop an alternative approach to homogeneity testing in the case of when an object space possesses a tangent space. This approach is based upon tangential components of our manifold-valued data and addresses non-uniqueness issues first observed in Paige and Patrangenaru (2023).

In particular, tangential components are basis-dependent. This non-uniqueness issue also occurs in Euclidean statistics since the choice of basis is a concern in multivariate analyses. A coordinate-free approach, however, has been used extensively in theoretical linear models, see for instance Wichura (2006). In our setting, we develop a coordinate-free approach to object data homogeneity testing based upon orthogonal projection operators.

Assume that for a given data set and embedding, two tangential components, say X and \tilde{X} , correspond to the same point on a Grassmann manifold $G_{k,m-k}$, which is the space whose points are k -planes or k -dimensional hyperplanes (containing the origin) in \mathbb{R}^m . We may denote columnspace of X as $C(X)$ and note that it corresponds to a k -plane. We then have that $C(X) = C(\tilde{X})$ since for each k -plane, $C(X)$, in $G_{k,m-k}$ is in a one-to-one correspondence with a unique $m \times m$ orthogonal projection matrix P idempotent of rank k onto $C(X)$.

As such,

$$P = X (X^T X)^{-1} X^T = \tilde{X} (\tilde{X}^T \tilde{X})^{-1} \tilde{X}^T = \tilde{P}$$

where \tilde{P} is orthogonal projection matrix rank k onto $C(\tilde{X})$.

Note that if the columns of an $m \times k$ orthonormal matrix Y spans $C(X)$ then

$$Y Y^T = P$$

and so we define

$$Y = X (X^T X)^{-1/2}.$$

In a similar fashion, we may define

$$\tilde{Y} = \tilde{X} (\tilde{X}^T \tilde{X})^{-1/2}$$

which satisfies

$$\tilde{Y} \tilde{Y}^T = \tilde{P}.$$

Here Y and \tilde{Y} are a points on the Stiefel manifold $V_{k,m}$, the space of all k -frames in \mathbb{R}^m , $k \leq m$. Let $M(m, k)$ denote the set of all $m \times k$ real matrices. Then Stiefel manifold $V_{k,m}$ is embedded in $M(m, k)$ by the inclusion map which is isometric mapping.

Guo et al. (2023) note that Euclidean space has a strong negative type, therefore if $j : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ is an isometric embedding of a metric space (\mathcal{M}, ρ) into an Euclidean space, (\mathcal{M}, ρ) inherits the strong negative type property from the Euclidean space in which it is embedded. It turns out that one ramification of this property is that the extrinsic energy distance $\varepsilon_j(Q_1, Q_2)$ on a metric space embedded into an Euclidean space vanishes if and only if the distributions Q_1 and Q_2 of two random objects on \mathcal{M} are equal.

2. Embeddings

Extrinsic shape analysis involves embedding manifold-valued data into an Euclidean space of some kind. An embedding of a differentiable manifold X into a differentiable manifold

Y is an injective map that has a one-to-one tangent map and for which the topology of the image space of X is the induced topology from Y .

As such, an isometric embedding is often considered since it preserves path lengths, angles, areas and volumes. The Nash Embedding Theorem (Nash, 1956) tells us that any manifold with a Riemannian structure can be isometrically embedded in some Euclidean space of high enough dimension.

For projective shape analysis, sample spaces consist of Cartesian products of manifold $\mathbb{R}P^2$, the real projective plane. $\mathbb{R}P^2$ is a Riemannian manifold that is equivalent to \mathbb{S}^2 with the antipodal points identified and we shall denote the points in $\mathbb{R}P^2$ as $[[x]]$. Paige and Patrangenaru (2024) derive a Nash embedding for projective space $\mathbb{R}P^2$ which is then used to derive an Nash embedding for projective shape space $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$.

2.1 Veronese-Whitney Embedding

The Veronese-Whitney (VW) embedding is the only embedding used in projective shape analysis prior to Nash embedding from Paige and Patrangenaru (2024). It is given as

$$j ([[x]]) = xx^T \quad (2)$$

where $x^T x = 1$ and it embeds $\mathbb{R}P^2$ into $Sym(3, \mathbb{R})$, the Euclidean space of 3×3 symmetric matrices with real entries.

2.2 Infimum Dimension Nash Embedding for $\mathbb{R}P^2$

In Paige and Patrangenaru (2024) this embedding is derived as

$$j ([[x]]) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} (x_1^2 - x_2^2) \\ x_1 x_3 \\ \frac{1}{2\sqrt{3}} (2x_3^2 - x_1^2 - x_2^2) \\ x_2 x_3 \\ x_1 x_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

It embeds $\mathbb{R}P^2$ into \mathbb{R}^5 .

2.3 Vech(VW) Embedding

We also consider the vech of the Veronese-Whitney (VW) embedding which is given as

$$j([x]) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1^2 \\ x_1 x_2 \\ x_1 x_3 \\ x_2^2 \\ x_2 x_3 \\ x_3^2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

and it embeds $\mathbb{R}P^2$ into \mathbb{R}^6 .

2.4 \mathbb{R}^4 Embedding

Finally, we consider the well-known embedding of $\mathbb{R}P^2$ of into \mathbb{R}^4 that is given as

$$j([x]) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1^2 - x_2^2 \\ x_1 x_2 \\ x_1 x_3 \\ x_2 x_3 \end{bmatrix}.$$

3. Tangential Components

The tangential components for the VW embedded data is given in Patrangenaru and Ellingson (2015). Here we provide a brief discussion of tangential components for the vector-valued embeddings into \mathbb{R}^d that include the Nash, vech(VW) and \mathbb{R}^4 embeddings with $d = 5, 6$ and 4 , respectively.

Let $Y_a = j(X_a)$, with $a = 1, \dots, n$ for some embedding j , then since the sample mean \bar{Y} ;

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n j(X_i) \quad (3)$$

lies in the ambient space it converges almost surely to mean $\tilde{\mu} = E[j(X_1)]$, the expectation of the embedded $\mathbb{R}P^2$ random variable. Let P now denote the projection map from the set of j nonfocal points in \mathbb{R}^d to $j(\mathbb{R}P^2) \subset \mathbb{R}^d$. If P is regarded as a differentiable function from \mathbb{R}^d to \mathbb{R}^d , then the range of the differential $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}$ is valued in T , the tangent space to $j(\mathbb{R}P^2)$ at $P(\tilde{\mu})$. Note that random vector $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$ has a degenerate covariance matrix. To correct for this we consider the decomposition of $j(\mathbb{R}P^2)$ in \mathbb{R}^d into its tangential component and orthogonal complement (w.r.t. an orthonormal basis of T) in the tangent space to $\iota(\mathbb{R}P^2)$ in \mathbb{R}^d at $P(\tilde{\mu})$. We shall denote the tangential component of differential random vector $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$ as $\tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$. Then for large n ,

$$\sqrt{n} \{P(\bar{Y}) - P(\tilde{\mu})\} \approx \sqrt{n} \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}).$$

Furthermore, as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\sqrt{n} \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{D}} N_2(0, \tilde{\Sigma})$$

where

$$\tilde{\Sigma} = Cov\{\tan DP_{\mu}(Y_1 - \tilde{\mu})\}$$

is the covariance of the tangential component of the differential map for a single random observation.

In extrinsic shape analysis, tests are based on asymptotic chi-square statistics generated from tangential components. For instance, the one sample test $H_0 : \tilde{\mu} = \tilde{\mu}_0$ for data on $\mathbb{R}P^2$ is of the form

$$n \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}_0}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}_0)^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}_0}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}_0) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{D}} \chi_2^2$$

where $\hat{\Sigma}$ is the sample covariance of

$$\{\tan DP_{\mu_0}(Y_i - \tilde{\mu}_0) : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}.$$

Under the equality of m extrinsic means in $\mathbb{R}P^2$ with independent samples

$$\sum_{j=1}^m n_j \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y})^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y}) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{D}} \chi_{2(m-1)}^2$$

where now \bar{Y} is the sample mean of the combined data sets and $\hat{\Sigma}$ is now the sample covariance of

$$\{\tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(Y_{ji} - \bar{Y}) : i = 1, 2, \dots, n_j \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, m\}.$$

Finally, under the equality of m extrinsic means in $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$ with independent samples

$$\sum_{j=1}^m n_j \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y})^T \hat{\Sigma}_k^{-1} \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y}) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{D}} \chi_{2q(m-1)}^2$$

where $\hat{\Sigma}_k$ is the sample covariance of concatenated tangential components.

4. Applications and Monte Carlo Studies

4.1 BBC Actor's Data

We considered the BBC actor's data from Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005) which consists of seven frontal views and seven side views of the **same** actor posing in different disguises.

On each image six landmarks were recorded consisting of the four corners of the eyes, “canthus,” and two end points of the lips, “mouth edge points” as shown in the image below.

Here the four eye-corner landmarks were taken to be the projective frame which resulted in a 2-ad of $\mathbb{R}P^2$ data points for each image. The data is given in Table 3 of Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005) who considered a level $\alpha = 0.05$ parametric test and a bootstrap test for difference in mean projective shapes of the frontal and side views. Both methodologies lead to the same conclusion that the frontal and side views are of the same actor. Here, we came to the same conclusion, the correct conclusion, for the VW, Nash, vech(VW) and \mathbb{R}^4 embedding-based test statistics with observed values 4.896, 4.896, 4.849 and 4.920, respectively and a cutoff of $\chi_{4,0.95}^2 = 9.488$.

We choose as a possible competitor to the Extrinsic Energy Statistic (EE-test) in equation (??) to be the two sample Multiresponse Permutation Procedure (MRPP) (Mielke and Berry, 2001) for random objects $\{X_i\}$. The extension of this procedure for random objects is relatively straightforward with a choice of distance function.

Here we consider the performance of the EE-test and MRPP permutation procedures where we use embedded data of eight types: (i) VW embedded data (VW); (ii) VW tangential components (VW_{tan}); (iii) Nash embedded data (Nash); (vi) Nash tangential components (Nash_{tan}); (v) vech(VW) embedded data (vech(VW)); (vi) vech(VW) tangential

components ($\text{vech}(\text{VW})_{\text{tan}}$); (vii) \mathbb{R}^4 embedded data (\mathbb{R}^4) and (viii) \mathbb{R}^4 tangential components ($\mathbb{R}^4_{\text{tan}}$). Note that the Frobenius distance was assumed for the MRPP statistic in all settings. Also, the EE-test applied to tangential component data effectively assumed the identity embedding for j in equation (??).

Below is the table of homogeneity test p-values we obtained for the BBC actor’s data.

	VW	VW_{tan}	Nash	Nash_{tan}
MRPP	0.0241	0.2141	0.0269	0.2271
EE-test	0.0242	0.2253	0.0278	0.2178
	$\text{vech}(\text{VW})$	$\text{vech}(\text{VW})_{\text{tan}}$	\mathbb{R}^4	$\mathbb{R}^4_{\text{tan}}$
MRPP	0.0362	0.2236	0.1220	0.2180
EE-test	0.0380	0.2242	0.1197	0.2130

Here we see that all of the embedded data procedures, with the exception for the \mathbb{R}^4 embedded-based procedure, incorrectly concluded that there a statistically significant difference in the frontal view and side view distributions, whereas the tangential component data-based procedures correctly concluded there was no difference in these distributions.

Guo et al. (2023) present an example where a statistically significant difference in two population means was found when two population distributions are not found to be significantly different with embedded data-based EE-test. They conjecture that reason behind this “CC shape-ADHD Paradox” is the Kendall shape space the data lies is a 96 dimensional space which resulted in a loss of power for their EE test for homogeneity.

4.2 Simulated Power Values for Synthetic Facial Landmark Data

Here we consider a Monte Carlo study involved simulated facial landmark data. This method of simulation was also considered in Paige and Patrangenaru (2023) albeit for different statistical procedures than we consider here. Our Monte Carlo study simulates from the two populations generated by the randomly perturbing the 9 facial landmarks for the average white American male and female faces (Face Research Lab in the Institute of Neuroscience and Psychology at the University of Glasgow) as shown below

For each simulation run these pixel perturbations were bivariate and independent uniform realizations each over the interval $(-\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$. For each set of gender landmarks total of 4 bivariate uniform realizations were used. This is because we assumed certain symmetries in these perturbations in that landmarks 1 and 4 had the same perturbation, landmarks 2 and 3 had the same perturbation, landmarks 5, 6 and 7 have their own perturbation, and landmarks 8 and 9 have their own perturbation. In our Monte Carlo study we had 400 runs in which independent samples of size 100 for each set of gender landmarks was performed.

We took landmark points 1, 4, 8 and 9 to be our projective frame from which we generated our projective coordinates; see Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005). Also ε was set equal to 20 and to 40. Numerical experimentation and visual inspection indicated that this might be a reasonable range of natural landmark variation from person to person.

Note that the simulated significance levels for the sixteen procedures we consider are not shown but did not differ significantly from nominal value 0.05. The tables below give the simulated power values for each of the sixteen procedures we consider with $\varepsilon = 20$ and 40, respectively.

Statistical Power with $\varepsilon = 20$

	VW	VW _{tan}	Nash	Nash _{tan}
MRPP	0.315	1.0	0.315	1.0
EE-test	0.3175	1.0	0.3225	1.0
	vech(VW)	vech(VW) _{tan}	\mathbb{R}^4	\mathbb{R}^4_{tan}
MRPP	0.3625	1.0	0.2175	1.0
EE-test	0.365	1.0	0.2125	1.0

Statistical Power with $\varepsilon = 40$

	VW	VW _{tan}	Nash	Nash _{tan}
MRPP	0.1125	0.3425	0.1125	0.335
EE-test	0.1125	0.3425	0.1125	0.3425
	vech(VW)	vech(VW) _{tan}	\mathbb{R}^4	\mathbb{R}^4_{tan}
MRPP	0.125	0.2825	0.125	0.2825
EE-test	0.1275	0.2875	0.1275	0.2875

Here we see that tangential component-based procedures provide a statistically significant increase power in comparison to embedding-based procedures. Furthermore, the VW and Nash embeddings yielded the most powerful procedures. Finally, as expected there was uniformly less statistical power as variability parameter ε increased from 20 to 40.

5. Conclusions

Our Monte Carlo studies show that we obtain more powerful homogeneity tests when we use embedding-based tangential components in place of the embedded data itself. Furthermore, in the application involving the BBC actor's data we saw that the embedded data procedures incorrectly concluded that there a statistically significant difference in the frontal view and side view distributions, whereas the tangential component data procedures correctly concluded there was no difference in these distributions.

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